

The Political, Spiritual, and Educational Activities of Our Enlightened Jadids in the Years Following the Establishment of Soviet Rule in Turkestan

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Abstract: the article provides information on the origin, activities of jadid and jadidism and their views on the issues of youth education, morality, etiquette, and knowledge, as well as provides the necessary information about the emergence of jaid in the form of the jadidist movement in our country during the national renaissance.

Keywords: national renaissance in our country of the 20th century, jadid," there is no future without historical memory"," Shuroi Islamiya "Munavvarqori, Abduraufqoriyev, Ubaydullakhoja Asadullakhojayev)," Shoroi Ulama","Turon".

The main focus on the development of the state after the independence of our country was on the restoration of our past true history, combined with the development of political, economic, social spheres in a wide range. The restoration of historical history was carried out by the first president of our country I.A.Karimov An example of this is the publication of Karimov's own work, "Tarixiy hotirasiz kelajak yo'q". In particular, this work gives some information about the scientific principles that our Jadids left in history, about their struggle for the independence of the land. Let us pay special attention to the history of the origin of this movement.

The jadidism movement of 1917 entered its new phase. After the February Revolution, Uzbek, tatar and Kazakhs make a pact to unite, and the society "Shuroi Islamiya" was formed on the ground of the Association "Turon" (the founders were Munavvarqori, Abdurauf Qoriyev, Ubaydullakhoja Asadullakhojayev). The society, which began its work on March 14, 1917, was charged with sending propagandists to villages and towns to lead an explanation of freedom, equality, to provide information about the election. His program was written by Munavvarqori. The jadids became the initiators of the creation of the "Shuroi Islomiya" system in places. The movement to give Turkestan the status of autonomy became a struggle for Turkestan independence.

The idea of uniting Turkic peoples took a strong place from the agenda. The issue of uniting single peoples and building a federated or autonomous state on this basis went to the fore, such as Uzbek, Kazakh, Kyrgyz, Karakalpak, Bashkir, Tatar, Turkmen. However, in the words of Munavvarqori, many people did not understand the difference between the Republic and autonomy. In particular, Turkestan figures were not fully prepared for the establishment of a truly meaningful Republic and the organization of its state composition. Kazakh and Bashkir figures – Mustafa Cho'qay, Zakiy Validiy and others-came to Turkestan and began to work

together with local jadids, when they felt that Petersburg would never give them both independence and autonomy.

In addition to “Shoroi Islomiya”, “Turon”, “Shoroi Ulamo”, “Ittifoqi musulimin”, “Gayrat” in Kokand, “Yosh Buxoroliklar” in Bukhara, “Yosh Xivaliklar” in Khiva, organizations such as “Ittifoq”, “Mirvaj ul-Islam”, “Miftah ul-maorif” began operating in Samarkand. In determining the socio-political orientation of these, Munavvarqori, Ubaydullakhoja Asadullakhojayev, Mahmudkhoja Behbudiy, Majid Qori Qadiriy, Ashurali Zohiriy, Zakiy Validiy, Mustafa Cho‘qay, Fitrat, Fayzulla Khojaev, Usmankhoja Po‘latkhojayev, Sherali Lapin, Mirkomilboy Mirmoinboyev, Obidjan Mahmudov, Polvonniyoz hoji Yusupov, Toshpolatbek Norbotabekov and others showed activity.

On the initiative of “Shoroi Islomiya”, the 1st Congress of Muslims of all Turkestan was convened on April 16-22, 1917. Among several issues, the participants of the Congress also discussed the issue of the state status of the Turkestan country. At the 1st Congress, it was decided to establish the Turkestan regional Muslim Salt (Kraymussovet) – a National Center. The chairman of the National Center is Mustafa Cho‘qay, who is succeeded by Validiy and Asadullakhojayev. This, along with the unification of the organizations, would trace the National Liberation Movement and centralize it organizationally.

At the meeting of the National Center on June 12, 1917, a regulation is adopted on the subordination of all societies and associations to The Salt of Central Muslim deputies. The aim of the centre was to give full rights to the lowest strata of the people – mercenaries and peasants-and to educate Turkestan Muslims culturally, scientifically, economically and ideologically.

Between April and June 1917, the jadids defined most political issues and their attitudes towards them. Ultimately, they realized that the political situation for territorial autonomy had matured.

The issue of autonomy became more serious as a result of the impetus given by the 1st Congress of all Russian Muslims in Moscow on May 1-11, 1917. On July 12-14, 1917, the Congress of Muslim organizations in Fergana addressed programmatic issues. It adopted the program (regulations) of the faction” Turkish Adami centrality (Federalists) ” and its charter of 22 articles.

On September 17-20, 1917, at the Congress of Muslims of Turkestan and Kazakhstan held in Tashkent, it was agreed to form a political party “Union musulimin” by combining “Shuroy Islimiya” and “Shoroi Ulamo”, “Turon” and other political organizations.

The issue of the form of Turkestan rule was the focus of the extraordinary 4th congress of Turkestan O'kka Muslims, which was held in Kokand on November 26-28, 1917. Everyone supported the idea of declaring autonomy and independence. The Government of the autonomy of Turkestan (chairman – Muhammadjan Tinishboyev, then Mustafa Cho‘qay) was established. Jadid poets like Fitrat, Cho‘lpan, Hamza applauded Turkestan autonomy, the lines ended.

After the establishment of the Soviet government, the jadidism movement underwent a strong change in February 1918, when the autonomy of Turkestan was soaked in blood by the Bolsheviks. While a large part of the Turkestan jadids, who did not want to compromise with the Soviet regime, operated in the ranks of the independence movement and in secret national organizations, some were forced to start work in the offices of the Soviet government.

The situation in the emirate of Bukhara and the Khanate of Khiva was somewhat different. In 1920, the Red Army invaded the territory of both states. The Bukhara people's Soviet republic and the Khorezm people's Soviet republic were formed, and the jadids came to power. Hence,

from 1920, the jadidist movement entered a new stage of its development, the path of compromise with the Soviets.

On September 1-7, 1920, the Congress of the people of the East was convened in Baku. The decisions made at the Congress played a certain role in the further fate of the Turkestan peoples. It was attended by a total of 90 people from Turkestan Nation devotees including Munavvarqori, Turor Risqulov, Cho'ipan, Salimkhan Tillakhanov, Rajab Muhamedov, Ququlilla Yunusov, Toshpolatbek Norbotabekov, Obidjon Mahmudov, Toraqul Jonuzakov, Zayniddin qori Nasriddinov, Hoji Safo Joraboyev, Ghazi Yunus. Anwar Pasha, who came from Turkey and personally sent Lenin himself, also took part in the work of the Congress. However, it became clear at the meetings that this Congress was a protest of the Bolsheviks against England. Therefore, 40 delegates from Turkestan held a mutual Council after the end of the Congress, in which they were concerned about the escalation of "propaganda work against Soviet power in Turkestan" and "raising a nationwide uprising on the day of the third anniversary of the October Revolution". However, their plan did not fully materialize.

Turkestan jadids have formed groups such as "Turon kuchi", "Turk kuchi", "Temur", "Izchilar", "Lochin", whose activities cover the entire territory, working on a program close to the English scouting school program. These groups, in addition to high school education, trade, art, were engaged in military exercises and began to be seen as the main striking force on the shoals. In 1920, the Soviet regime ended the activities of these groups.

The end of the events in Fergana and Tashkent could not quench the jadids' hopes. They started working together with the leaders of the Republic of Bukhara. In Bukhara, the jadid progressive faction was formed. According to the program of this faction, it was envisaged that the state would be headed by the president of the Republic (President) and the parliament.

On August 2-5, 1921, an organization of Turkestan national unity was formed in Bukhara, headed by Validiy. He plays an important role in the cipsification of the independence movement. The Turkestan national unity organization and the Munavvarqori-led organization "Milliy Ittihod" (formed in 1919) worked together. The main goal of both organizations was to preserve the Republic of Bukhara, in general, from the influence of the Sovietization and Russification of the Turkestan region, to achieve the independence of Turkestan. In 1925, on the basis of the organization "Milliy Ittihod", the organization "Milliy iistiqlol" is formed.

In his last years, The Last Years of the Jadidism movement are not characterized by active political struggles. During this period, the Soviet regime set about mass repression of the National intelligentsia, composing various political affairs "O'n sakkizlar guruhi", "Inog'omovchilik", "Qosimovchilik", "Badriddinovchilik" and others). In November 1929, a strong blow was dealt to the jadidism movement with the imprisonment of 38 people led by Munavvarqori (who later grew to 87).

The jadidist movement was able to rise from political enlightenment to the level of the Jadid progressive faction. This movement, as well as the members of the faction, according to their activities and program, were not "representatives of the liberal bourgeoisie, serving the benefit of a handful of the rich," as they say in the literature of Sho'ro, but rather representatives of the democratic process, who thought about the fate of all the peoples of Turkestan.

As Soviet power in Turkestan was forcibly established, a number of jadids withdrew from active political life and engaged only in artistic creation (Abdulvohid Burhonov, Abdullah Avloni, Sadriddin Ayniy, etc. Some jadids labored in the cultural and educational shrines of the Soviet authorities (Ubaydullakhoja Asadullakhojayev, Munavvarqori, Hamza, Sa'dullakhoja Tursunkhojayev, Toshpulatbek Norbotabekov, etc. Some jadids continued to work in high state and government positions as "local communists" (Fayzulla Khojaev, Abdulqodir Muhiddinov, Nizamiddin Khojaev, etc). In the case of some jadids, he joined the

ranks of the independence movement in Turkestan and left for emigration abroad (Usmonkhoja Po'latkhojaye, Sadriddinkhan Sharifkhojaye, Abdulhamid Oripov, etc).

All prominent figures of the jadidist movement (except Sadridin Ayni) were killed in the 30s as a result of a massacre carried out by the Soviet mustabid regime. The jadidism movement was branded "millatchilik", panturkism, panislamism during the Soviet period and condemned. Jadid literature was banned from reading.

In conclusion, it can be said that literature written during the Soviet period described jadidism as a "bourgeois-liberal movement". After the disintegration of the USSR, the name of the jadidist movement and its exponents was revived. Historian, literary scholar, linguist, philosopher, jurist, art historian and pedagogical scholars have obtained early results in the study of the scientific and literary heritage of jadids.

During the years of independence, the works of Fitrat, Cho'lpn, Abdulla Avloniy in 2 volumes, Behbudiy, Abdullah Qadiri, Sidqi Khondayliqiy, Ibrat, Ajziy, Sofizoda in 1 volume, as well as Fayzulla Khojaev, Munavvarqori, Polvonniyoz hoji Yusupov were published. 20 famous representatives of the jadids were included "Unutilmas siymolar". Jadidchilik harakatining namoyandalari" (Tashkent, 1999) album-book out of print. Their activities were included in textbooks and manuals.

On September 16-18, 1999, Tashkent hosted an international conference on "Central Asia at the beginning of the 20th century: the struggle for reform, renewal, development and independence (solidarity, autonomy, independence)", where influential scientists from the United States, Germany, France, Italy, the Netherlands, Turkey, Russia, India and other countries exchanged views with their colleagues on the latest conclusions gathered in world science about acts of jadidism and independence. It was recognized that the jadidism movement is a phenomenon of global importance. The conference established an international scientific council researching this problem.

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